

WORKPLACE DIVERSITY MANAGEMENT AND PERFORMANCE OF STATE UNIVERSITIES IN ANAMBRA AND ENUGU STATES, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15441325>

Abstract: The study examined the effect of workplace diversity management on performance of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria. The specific objectives include; examine the effect of experience diversity on career development and ascertain the effect of ethnic diversity on quality of research output of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria. The study used survey research design. Population of the study was 2,650 and sample size of the study was 348 using Taro Yamani's formula. Instrument used for data collection was the questionnaire. The reliability coefficient of questionnaire was 0.70 and this was measured using Cronbach's alpha coefficient which showed consistency of the instrument. Simple regression analytical tool was used in testing the hypotheses. Based on data analysis, findings revealed that experience diversity had a significant positive effect on career development of State Universities in Nigeria ($F(3,184) = 47.403, p < 0.05$) and ethnic diversity had a significant positive effect on quality of research output of State Universities in Nigeria ($F(3,184) = 4.035; p < 0.05$). Based on the findings and conclusion reached, the study recommended that universities management should not only be committed to initiate experience workers, but should also uphold its best practice and be highly committed in doing so. And also Universities management should decentralized ethnic components common culture, tradition, customs, routine practice, costumes, beliefs, and values among workers in order to them have equal mind set during discharging of their duties.

Keywords: Workplace Diversity, Career Development, Ethnic Diversity, Research Output, University Performance.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern globalized and interconnected world, universities have come to recognize the crucial role of workplace diversity in driving improved students academic performance and organizational success. Extensive academic research and industry literature have highlighted the manifold benefits that diverse workforces bring, including heightened creativity, enhanced decision-making, and superior problem-solving capabilities (Wadhwa, 2022).

The workplace is becoming more and more diverse than ever, owing to the impact of worldwide economic integration, also known as globalization, which has now made the world a global village. Workplace diversity has several dimensions ranging from ethnic to linguistic, national, economic, and organizational cultures. No

doubt, globalization is an on-going process that is concretizing the linkages between people, cities, neighborhoods, regions, as well as countries closer together than they have ever been before (UNESCO, 2013). In 1999, an important step was made to deal with the issues of diversity, equity and inclusion, with a constitutional clause expressly prohibiting discrimination on the basis of community, ethnicity, place of origin, gender, religion and political opinion. In recent years, attempts have also been made to introduce legislations that specifically address different dimensions of diversity: age, gender, disability and sexual orientation (Adeleye *et al.*, 2014).

Therefore, it has been opined that many modern work universities have people of variegated cultural backgrounds working together as employees which may be a potential source of organizational conflict (Ukachukwu & Iherionhanna, 2023). During the medieval times, the university structure is being described as simple and uncomplicated. But today, the simple and uncomplicated relationships of the medieval university had given way to a complex organization. In other words, the university started as a single community, a community of master and students being held together by a common name, a common governing body and related purpose. Today university is viewed as multiversity rather than university because at its large components and varied interests such as internal stakeholders, external stakeholders, national and international components (Ile, 2014).

The university is a unique organization concerned with the creation of knowledge through research. Dissemination of knowledge through teaching, preservation of knowledge through its libraries; serving the needs of the society through its public service, community services and foster relationships with other bodies outside the university community. The rapid growth of global and international higher education system has put colleges and university under pressure. A number of ever rising numbers of institutions are chasing limited pool of talents and funding. In this competitive environment, raising the profile of an institution is crucial (Sarstedt, 2017).

There is needs for the University to realize it vision of creating a core functional, globally competitive and research focused University which is not only just an ivory tower but responsive to the needs of society while delivering word class education and knowledge. It is therefore, very imperative for the University to communicate the vision, mission and objectives of the University which is not only responsive to the needs of the society but also the demands of global education and knowledge in line with her basic objectives of seeking the truth, teaching the truth and preserving the truth (Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2020).

Improved performance can provide the Universities with a competitive advantage by allowing it to differentiate itself from its competitors. This can also lead to increased market share, students' loyalty, innovativeness and positive reputation (Zhang, 2020; Al-Qatan, 2019). It is against this background that the researcher wishers to x-rayed the effect of workplace diversity management on performance of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The management of workforce diversity as a tool to increase organizational effectiveness cannot be underscored, especially with current changes sweeping across the globe. Owing to this, there is need to

investigate the awareness of managers on certain skills necessary for the creation of a diverse workforce environment. In recent years diversity management and workforce diversity have been substantial and as such have forced companies to embrace these concepts in their companies with the aim of increasing productivity and profit. This forced integration has created divergence and uncertainty in the workforce, as management is not skilled enough to control the concept of diversity management and its ethics, and so managers are finding it difficult to effectively practice diversity management, which in turn has become an albatross on their neck.

Despite organizations investing millions in workforce diversity to boost employee morale and improve performance, they rarely achieve their expected benefits. With an extremely heterogeneous workforce in terms of race, ethnicity, culture, language, sexual orientation, religion, conceptions, business organizations face a very complex task to safeguard society or business organizations from potentially destructive conflicts that arise easily in a radically pluralistic or diverse organization. The situation has led most Universities to experience insecure employee commitment, decreased career development, interrupted academic programme, poor quality of university graduates and decreased students' enrollment to the Universities.

Sequel to the above mentioned inevitable conscienceless, it is reasonable to presume that the optimum performance in Universities will be achieved, if management team understood the importance of properly managing the diversity of the people in their universities. Many studies on workplace diversity have looked at its dimensions with the aim of getting statistics of the issues. Therefore, this study x-rayed the effect of workplace diversity management on performance of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

Broad objective of the study is to examine effect of workplace diversity on performance of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria. Specific objectives were to;

- i. Examine the effect of experience diversity on career development of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria.
- ii. Ascertain the effect of ethnic diversity on quality of research output of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States of Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

This article will be beneficial to the government and policymakers, who will ensure that beyond having a diverse workforce, diversity management policies should be made and adhered to; for the employers of different sectors, it will aid them to enhance commitment from their diverse employees; and for the Academics and Researchers, the article will guide them to further explore on deficient areas, as effective management of diversity has the potential to deliver positive changes in the near future.

The study centered more on academic and none academic staff in order to observe how workplace diversity management works across State Universities. The Universities are Enugu State University of Science and Technology located at Agbani, Enugu State and Chukwemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University formerly Anambra State University located at Uli Anambra State. The study also covered only two independent variables which are experience diversity and ethnic diversity against career development and quality of research output as

dependent variables which is University performance.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Workplace

A workplace is a location where someone works, for their employer or themselves, a place of employment. Such a place can range from a home office to a large office building or factory. A workplace or place of employment is a location where people perform tasks, jobs and projects for their employer. Types of workplaces vary across industries and can be inside a building or outdoors. Workplaces can be mobile, and some people may work in different locations on various days (Tsui and Gutek, 2020).

Diversity

Traditionally, the term diversity has been widely used to refer to the demographic composition of a workforce. Some studies have looked at diversity using the compositional approach, otherwise known as Surface-level diversity (SLD) or demographic diversity, which refers to the extent to which a unit is heterogeneous on characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, religion, age, functional background, and organizational tenure (Tsui and Gutek, 2020).

Management

Ile (2003) define management as the combination and utilization of other organization's resources by people through the process of planning, organizing, staffing, directing, controlling and co-ordinating so as to achieve its objectives. It is a process of process of planning, organization, organizing, staffing, directing, controlling and co-ordinating the effects of organizational goals.

Workplace Diversity

To Daft (2018) Workforce diversity refers to a workforce made up of people with different human qualities or who belong to various cultural groups. The author regarded individual diversity to include people different from themselves along the dimensions such as social background. Workforce diversity as noted by Robbins and Judge (2021) acknowledges a workforce which comprised women and men. As the authors went on to observe, these individuals with variety of physical or psychological abilities. Diversity management is about finding ways to get the diverse contributions from employees.

Workplace Diversity Management

Workforce diversity management is the ability of a manager to achieve success for an organization by making the best of use of the similarities and differences among employees in terms of age, cultural background, physical abilities and disabilities, race, ethnicity, religion, sex, as well as in terms of personality, values, attitudes, perception and cognitive style. Individuals who think towards deep level diversity are more likely to perceive themselves as similar, rather than dissimilar, to members of their workgroup on unobservable qualities (Liao, *et. al*, 2018).

Gender Diversity

Gender refers to one self identity i.e. how much a person associates himself or herself with masculine or the feminine as prescribed by the society. These gender differences influence the approach in which individual react in workplace. Sometime gender diversity adversely affects the behaviors like discrimination, prejudice and stereotyping. Eventually such attitude negatively influences the efficiency at workplace (Shakeel, & Fazal, 2019).

Age Diversity

Age stereotypes exist for older as well as young workers and are both positive and negative. Kunze, (2019) organizations are facing the challenge of age diversity because it is natural that individuals inclined towards their own groups at the cost of other groups. Further maintained that if employee's age is set significant criteria for distinction, other age groups feel insecure and sense of emotional instability and discrimination developed inside the institutions (Shakeel, & Fazal, 2019).

Ethnic Diversity

Makokolo (2021) define ethnicity like tribal grouping enjoying common history of origination and develop sense of common fate. Timmermans, Ostergaard, & Kristinsson (2021) concluded that ethnicity may be considered as substitute or alternate for cultural background. The differences in the ethnicity can be brought innovative and creative performance among the members.

Experience Diversity

Workplace experience is referred as knowledge, proficiency and capabilities of a worker acquired during professional journey in a specific discipline (Carr, *et al*, 2020). Pinder (2024) asserted that experienced employees in any business are responsible for generating organizational income rather than production. Hiring of an employee having suffice knowledge, understanding the job requirements, targets and challenges associated with the jobs, is a key to success (Morgan, 2022; Ridhi & Sushant, 2024; Sayers, 2012; Creary *et al*, 2021; Trenerry *et al*, 2023; Pitts 2020; Emerson, *et al*, 2020; Khan, *et al*, 2019).

Performance

Performance is defined by Byrnes (2019) as the way to perform the job tasks according to the prescribed job description. Performance is the art of completing the task within the defined boundaries. Cascio (2020) defined performance as working effectively, which is the way somebody does a job, judged by its effectiveness. E.g academic excellence, quality in education, international student outlook, career development, quality of research output (Ayşen & Ozlem, 2009).

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored significantly on social identity theory of workplace diversity. This research focuses on social identity theory propounded by Tajfel's in 1982. Social Identity Theory which explains how workplace variety, such as age, gender, ethnicity, and experience, affects employee productivity. Three distinct theoretical frameworks are advocated by the phrase diversity's theoretical model. To begin, there is social categorization, which describes how individuals are classified based on social characteristics such as age, gender, and ethnicity, and how stereotypes are formed as a result of these differences (Hamdani & Buckley, 2011).

Empirical Review

Jasem, Alshemmari and Monawer (2024) examined analyzing the relationship between workplace diversity, experience diversity and innovation and its influence on organizational performance in Nigeria. Results indicate a significant positive relationship between workplace diversity, experience diversity and innovation, which in turn improves organizational performance.

Merlyn and Sulaiman (2024) studied addressing workplace diversity to improve employee performance: implications for SOEs in Namibia. The research aims to provide insights into the influence of specific workplace diversity dimensions such as age, educational background, ethnicity, gender, and religion on employee performance in the context of SOEs in Namibia. The findings indicate that age diversity and educational background diversity significantly influence employee performance in the participating SOEs.

Kabuoh, Adeoye and Barreto (2023) examined workplace diversity and innovativeness of selected private universities in Nigeria. The purpose of the study was to examine workplace diversity and innovativeness of private universities. The study adopted survey research design. The study found that workplace diversity has significant effect on innovativeness.

Ekejiuba, Muritala, Maitala and Nwoye (2023) investigated effect of workplace diversity management on employee commitment in the Nigerian Public Sector. The study main objective was to investigate the effect of workplace diversity management on employee commitment in Nigeria. The findings also revealed that workplace diversity management policies in multicultural nations like Nigeria were poorly implemented even though they existed, and this was reflected in lopsided appointments, promotions, and nominations at the top government level.

Ridhi and Sushant (2024) examined workforce diversity in higher education for sustainable employee performance in Punjab. The purpose of the study on workforce diversity in higher education is to look into the connection between employee performance in private colleges and workforce diversity. The study highlights how crucial it is to promote learning, value accumulated expertise, and assemble a varied workforce in order to create productive teams. To ensure the reliability of our findings across diverse educational settings, future research should consider data from various universities.

Gap in Empirical Review

The study has several areas that need more research. It does not have enough numerical data to back up its findings from interviews and surveys. It also does not compare its results to other universities, whether public or in different regions. The research only looks at a short period of time, so it cannot show the long-term effects of diversity programs. Additionally, the views of employees themselves are not included, only the perspectives of leaders and organizational processes. Finally, the study does not examine how different aspects of diversity, such as experience and ethnic, may interact and impact employee experiences. Filling these gaps by using more numerical measures, making comparisons, studying long-term changes, getting employee feedback, and looking at intersecting diversity factors would provide better insight into how a diverse workforce influences long-term employee performance in Universities. This gap study seeks to fill.

METHODOLOGY

Survey research design was adopted for the study. Creswell (2014) state that descriptive survey involves gathering data that describe events and then organizes, depicts, and describes the data collected without any manipulation. A survey research design is a design that studies both small and large population by collecting and analyzing data by the use of questionnaires or interview in order to make generalization or inferences. Survey research design is appropriate for any study that requires the opinion of respondents. Population of this study was two thousand six hundred and fifty (2,650) comprising of teaching and non teaching staff of the Universities studied. Sample size was 348. However, for inferential purposes and the empirical evaluation of the variables (predictor and criterion) of this study, simple regression analytical tool was used in order to ascertain the effect of dependent on independent variables under the study.

Test of Hypotheses

Test of Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Experience diversity does not have significant positive effect on career development of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria.

Table 1 ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 Regression	20.123	3	6.708	47.403	.000b
Residual	25.612	297	.142		
Total	45.735	300			

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: career development b. Predictors: (Constant), experience diversity Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (6.708) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.142), yielding $F=47.403$. From the results, the model in this table is statistically significant positive (Sig =.000). Therefore, experience diversity had a significant positive effect on career development at $F(3,184) = 47.403$.

Test of Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Ethnic diversity does not have significant positive effect on quality of research output of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria.

Table 2 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.250a	.065	.047	.45468

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2025

Predictors: (Constant), ethnic diversity. Table above revealed that there is a significant positive effect at $R = .250$ between ethnic diversity and quality of research output. An examination of the table shows that the R square = .063 which implies that ethnic diversity accounts for only 6.3% of variations having a significant positive effect on quality of research output of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria.

Table 3 ANOVA a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sign
1 Regression	2.503	3	.834	4.035	.000b
Residual	37.417	297	.207		
Total	39.921	300			

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025

a. Dependent Variable: ethnic diversity b. Predictors: (Constant), quality of research output, Table shows that the F-value is the Mean Square Regression (0.834) divided by the Mean Square Residual (0.207), yielding $F=4.035$. The model in this table shows that quality of research output statistically and significantly at (Sig =.000) and had a significant positive effect on ethnic diversity at $F(3,184) = 4.035$. The statistical results is given as; (aesthetics $\beta = .019$; $t = .171$; $p > 0.05$). The statistical result implies that ethnic diversity had significant positive effect on quality of research output of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

- i. Experience diversity had a significant positive effect on career development of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria ($F = 47.403$, $p < 0.000 < 0.05$).
- ii. Ethnic diversity had a significant positive effect on quality of research output of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria ($F = 4.035$; $p < 0.000 < 0.05$).

Conclusion

In a nutshell, the study concluded that workplace diversity management had a significant positive effect on performance of State Universities in Anambra and Enugu States, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Recommendations Following the conclusion above, this study recommends that:

- i. Universities management should not only be committed to initiate experience workers, but should also uphold its best practice and be highly committed in doing so.
- ii. Universities management should decentralized ethnic components common culture, tradition, customs, routine practice, costumes, beliefs, and values among workers in order to them have equal mind set during discharging of their duties.

Contributions to Knowledge

The study will contribute to the existing body of knowledge on workplace diversity and performance of state university in Nigeria. Specifically, the study will shed light on the effect of dependent and independent variables. The researcher contributed basically on model of workplace diversity and performance with statistical evidence which illustrated below;

Figure 5.1: Researcher Own Model

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